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Am I Truly the Brother of All? The Challenge of Paradoxical Responsibility

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Abstract: This is a study of the need for a peaceful and fraternal resolution of the world crisis we are in. It argues against any confrontational resolution of the conflict. Literature and literary minds see the issue as fratricidal way of domination and subjugation. The clash of civilisations simply another name of colonisation. We look for a human resolution which is ethical and of mutual respect and understanding. Pope Francis as spiritual leader is presenting the only alternative of human initiative of being an initiator which is that dialogue and fraternity.

Keywords: Barbarians, Civilizations, Christianity, Islam, Conflict and Conversation, Responsibility, *Fratelli Tutti*.

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1. Waiting for the Barbarians

In *Waiting for the Barbarians* (1980), J. M. Coetzee interrogates the foundations of imperial states by highlighting the differences from the barbarians that the anonymous Empire maintains. It is simply a parable of modern nations. This is true not only nations but even groups of ethnic, religious and caste identities. Coetzee's novel helps us in participating in resistance literature and critiquing imperialism. Said interpreting the novel says: "... narrative is crucial to my argument here, my basic point being that stories are at the heart of what explorers and novelist says about strange regions of the world; they also become the method colonized people use to assert their own identity and the existence of their own history. The main battle in imperialism is over land, of course, but when it came to who owned the land, who had the right to settle and work on it, who kept it going, who won it back, and who now plans its future—these issues were reflected, contested, and even for a time decided in narrative" (Said 1994: xii-xiii). Coetzee is questioning the bases of imperial identity. Such loose labels are clear when the magistrate who is the voice of conscience shifts the label —enemy, and implicitly —barbarian. The imperial perceptive on the other who is not one of same as its own is a view of enemy – barbarian. It is Manichaeian perceptive of the right against the wrong. It boldly asserts that, to be living in a world ruled by egoism, a world in which no one could feel the human element as the human element in others, [in which] each one [could feel it] immediately only in his own self." "Through torture, the Empire therefore tries to unmake the "voice," the expression of the "I" of the person. After this, the Empire can "reconstruct" it at pleasure, rewrite it according to its wishes and ... create them as its victims, controlling them in whatever it wants.

Once the voice is deconstructed, prisoners are left with just their injured body, and in this condition they become the slaves of their physical needs. Being left with just the body—what Descartes identified with the primary Other—prisoners then lack the element that supposedly distinguishes human beings from animals, and are finally turned into what the Empire has been waiting for: Barbarians and, in many cases of racist politics, subhuman beings” (Canepari-Labib 2005) The barbarian—is one who speaks a different language. Indeed, among the most identifiable marks of everyday foreignness are an accent, a mismanaged idiom, an alterity in expression: language bears a primary relation to foreignness. The magistrate tells the colonel, “Those pitiable prisoners you brought in—are they the enemy I must fear? Is that what you say? You are the enemy, Colonel! ‘I can restrain myself no longer. I pound the desk with my fist. You are the enemy, you have made the war, and you have given them all the martyrs they need—starting not now but a year ago when you committed your first filthy barbarities here! History will bear me out!’” (Coetzee 1999: 112). He is a voice of something different. “To the objectivism of war we oppose a subjectivity born from the eschatological vision” (Levinas 1969: 25). The tasks which face the human apparatus at the turning points of history cannot be solved by optical means—that is, by contemplation alone. For Levinas, there can be no end in sight—until this moral lucidity becomes the vigilance of a revolutionary messianic consciousness that finally breaks the spell of fatality, the “truth of being” operative in the triumph of the logic of identity, the ideology of totality and the rule of a cold objectivity (Levinas 1969: 21). And yet, even when we take seriously the unusual eschatology invoked here, between the thought of “an equitable life” and the thought with which John Rawls concludes *The Theory of Justice*, there can be only—as Kafka said of the Messiah’s intervention—the slightest difference. “The perspective of eternity is not a perspective from a certain place beyond the world, nor the point of view of a transcendent being; rather it is a certain form of thought and feeling that rational

persons can adopt within the world. And having done so, they can, whatever their generation, bring together into one scheme all individual perspectives and arrive together at regulative principles that can be affirmed by everyone as he lives by them, each from his own standpoint. Purity of heart, if one could attain it, would be to see clearly and to act with grace and self-command from this point of view” (Rawls 1978: 587).

2. The Clash of Civilizations

“The fundamental source of conflict in this new world will not be primarily ideological or primarily economic. The great divisions among humankind and the dominating source of conflict will be cultural. Nation states will remain the most powerful actors in world affairs, but the principal conflicts of global politics will occur between nations and groups of different civilizations. The clash of civilizations will dominate global politics. The fault lines between civilizations will be the battle lines of the future” (Huntington 1993: 22-49). The Clash of *Civilizations and the Remaking of World Order*, Huntington stated that, “this book is not intended to be a work of social science. It is instead meant to be an interpretation of the evolution of global politics after the Cold War. It aspires to present a framework, a paradigm, for viewing global politics that will be meaningful to scholars and useful to policymakers” (Huntington 1996: 13). Huntington’s “clash of civilizations” argument for electoral gain, what, more generally, has become of Huntington’s prophesy of civilizational conflicts between blocs of culturally-defined states? Huntington discussed two civilizational conflicts which he thought would be of great importance in post-Cold War international relations: fights between “Islam” and the West, and between China and the West. Huntington’s claim was not only that the West would be in conflict with “core” states of the Muslim world, such

as, potentially, Pakistan, Egypt Saudi Arabia, and Iran, but would also be at loggerheads with China, the “Sinic” civilization “core” state. Huntington would claim that the Muslim world “lacks the core political values that gave birth to representative democracy in Western civilization: separation of religious and secular authority, rule of law and social pluralism, parliamentary institutions of representative government, and protection of individual rights and civil liberties as the buffer between citizens and the power of the state.” Islamophobia has been growing since the early 1990s, exacerbated by 9/11 specifically and fears of Islamist terrorism generally. Islamophobia can be found across society but is increasingly evident in the right wing political parties across the globe. The underlying problem for the West is not Islamic fundamentalism. It is Islam, a different civilization whose people are convinced of the superiority of their culture and are obsessed with the inferiority of their power. It is the West, a different civilization whose people are convinced of the universality of their culture and believe that their superior, if declining, power imposes on them the obligation to extend that culture throughout the world. These are the basic ingredients that fuel conflict between Islam and the West. The right figures such as Gert Wilders in The Netherlands and Marine Le Pen in France. They claim that Europe’s Muslim immigrants pose a clear and persistent threat to “European” traditions of tolerance, freedom, and democracy. Everywhere in Europe such tendencies grow. The clash of civilizations paradigm is today helpful in explaining and accounting for electoral gains of right-wing populist politicians in various Western countries, including the USA, Hungary, Poland, and Slovenia. The new European right-wing populism has thus succeeded in rhetorically reconciling Christianity and secularism as markers of a claimed “civilized” identity, while simultaneously merging Islam and specific “Oriental” ethnic features as key signs of barbarism.

3. The Myth of 'The Clash of Civilizations'

- i. The notion that civilizations are monolithic and homogeneous and it is assumed the unchanging character of the duality between us and them. Huntington defines Islamic civilization reductively, as if what most matters about it is its supposed anti-Westernism. It doesn't matter to him that Muslims have other things to do than to think about the West with hatred, how to destroy the West, bomb it and destroy the whole world really.
- ii. There is blind assumption that Islam has never modernized, that it never separated between Church and State, that it's incapable of understanding other civilization, all of them complete untruths. Of course the Arabs, Muslims have travelled well before the Europeans in the East, in Africa, and in Europe and were great discoverers of other civilizations well before Marco Polo and Columbus. For him Islam, Confucianism, and the other five or six civilizations, Hindu, Japanese, Slavic, Orthodox, Latin American and African that still exist, are separate from each other and consequently potentially in a conflict, which he wants to manage, not resolve. He writes therefore as a crisis manager.
- iii. Is it wise to produce a simplified map of the world and then hand it to generals and civilian lawmakers as a prescription for first comprehending and then acting in the world? Doesn't it mobilize nationalist passions and therefore nationalist murderousness? Shouldn't we be asking the question, to mitigate or to aggravate the likelihood of conflict?
- iv. There is colonising mentality. Perhaps the most famous of such devices is French notion of the civilizing mission a notion underlying which is the idea that some races and cultures have a higher aim in

life than others. This gives the more powerful, the more developed, the more civilized, the higher, the right to colonize others, not in the name of brute force, or plunder.

- v. The conquest of the Earth mentality which mostly means the taking it away from those who have a different complexion, a slightly flatter noses than ourselves is not a pretty thing, when you look into it too much. What redeems it, is the idea. An idea at the back of it, not a sentimental pretence but an idea, and an unselfish belief in the idea, something you can bow down before and sacrifice to. Where is our ethical or spiritual calibre?

- vi. The Clash of Civilization argument completely forgets the counter-culture in the mainstream or official cultures. There are dissenting or alternative, unorthodox, heterodox, strands that contain many anti-authoritarian themes in them that are in competition with the official culture. No culture is understandable without some sense of this ever-present source of creative provocation from the unofficial to the official. To disregard the sense of restlessness in the West, in Islam, in Confucianism within each culture and to assume that there's complete homogeneity between culture and identity, is to miss what is vital and fertile in culture. To emphasize the differences between cultures is completely to ignore the literally unending debate about defining the culture or civilization within those civilizations including western ones. These debates completely undermine any idea of a fixed identity and hence the relationships between identities. What culture today, whether Japanese, Arab, European, Korean, Chinese, Indian, has not had long intimate and extraordinarily rich contacts with other cultures?

- vii. The work of man is only just beginning and it remains to conquer all the violence entrenched in the recesses of our passion and no race possess the monopoly of beauty, of intelligence, of force, and there's a place for all at the rendezvous of victory and what they imply. There are kinds of benign globalism already to be found for instance in the environmental movement, in scientific cooperation, in the women's movement, and the universal concern for human rights, in concepts of global thought that stress community and sharing over racial, gender or class dominance. It would seem that there are efforts to return the community of civilizations and incitements to wasteful conflicts and un-edifying chauvinisms and that seems to be exactly what we don't need.

4. The Measure of Our Responsibility

As humans, we come into the world as “*initium*, newcomers and beginners”; we are beginners accomplishing newness. This state of being-beginners is essential to the human condition, and by means of it we “take initiative, are prompted into action” (Arendt 1958: 177). “Unexpectedness” and “natality” and the call for newness and the expansion of meanings is to resist the pressure of fatality of politics and to envision creative ways of engaging with new generations in the concrete and crucial practice of coming into the world. This is what Pope Francis does in his encyclical *Tutti Fratelli*. He is entering history to change history of civilizational hatred to a call to a civilisation of cooperation, dialogue and fraternity.

It is a dreadful evil when a man measures his behaviour to his fellow humans. It is as if he were always manipulating weights and measures. Plato told us that God is man's measure. “For the little humanity that adorns the earth, a relaxation [relâchement] of essence . . . is needed: in the just

war waged against war to tremble or shudder at every instant because of this very justice. This weakness is needed. This relaxation of virility without cowardice is needed for the little cruelty our hands repudiate” (Levinas 1981: 185). Moreover, the “presence” of the other is “infinite”, and constitutes for me an “infinite” obligation. As “infinite”, this “presence” is also a certain “absence”, and consequently it exceeds all measure—not only my own, but all conceivable, all possible measures. Ethical life can only be a question, for Levinas, of “measuring oneself against the perfection of the infinite” (Levinas 1987: 58). “We must be human. We need eternity, for it alone provides our gestures room; and yet we know ourselves in cramped finality. We must, then, create an infinity within these barriers, since we no longer believe in boundlessness” (Rilke 1977: 37).

The measure Pope Francis presents is not a doctrine but a story. The story of the Good Samaritan is constantly being repeated with ever new interpretations. “All of us have in ourselves something of the wounded man, something of the robber, something of the passers-by, and something of the Good Samaritan” (FT69). It is through the story the future is foreseen as an insight. It is fundamental metaphor. “Metaphor remains, in all its essential characteristics, a classical philosopheme” wrote Derrida (1982: 219). It is his 'White Mythology'. A natural explanation of this is that metaphor is uniquely paradoxical, and uniquely disturbing to philosophy. “We can see this clearly as social and political inertia is turning many parts of our world into a desolate byway, even as domestic and international disputes and the robbing of opportunities are leaving great numbers of the marginalized stranded on the roadside.” (FT 71)

What we imagine we become, is our world facing a great concern of the “clash of civilizations”? If we imagine we become, are we people of different cultures which hate, insult, and slaughter each other, and struggle to protect our own interests (think of the Rwanda genocide). Surely, this is the reason why Samuel Huntington said in his article *The Clash of Civilizations and the*

Remaking of World Order: “Nation states are and will remain the most important actors in world affairs, but their interests, associations, and conflicts are increasingly shaped by cultural and civilizational factors.” But can we imagine the world differently? The totally new that the Pope initiates is that the essential thing was that our way of life was the most true, good, beautiful, and efficient, and that the beliefs, values, and practices of others, insofar as they are different from ours are not false, shameful, unpleasant and irrational. This is bias and myth from which we have to free ourselves. We need a story that seeks to see the affairs of the global world “with the eyes of others” uniting historians from various parts of the world.

The pope is joining the world religions which is positive step to address the world problems. There is positive thinking which is not an attitude ruled by egoism, a world in which “no one could feel the human element as the human element in others, in which each one [could feel it] immediately only in his own self” (Rosenzweig 1971: 82). “The tasks which face the human apparatus at the turning points of history cannot be solved by optical means—that is, by contemplation alone. They are acquired gradually by habit, under the tutelage of tactile reception” (Benjamin 1969: 240). The moral lucidity becomes the vigilance of a “revolutionary messianic consciousness that finally breaks the spell of fatality, the “truth of being” operative in the triumph of the logic of identity, the ideology of totality and the rule of a cold objectivity” (Levinas 1969: 21).

The Pope proposes an understanding which is a dimension of our “spiritual nature”. In this sense, human history is a spiritual work (Levinas 1990: 91). History as a relationship among human beings ignores a position of the I before the other [*l'autre*] in which the other remains transcendent with respect to me. I am not exterior to history, I do find in the

Other a point that is absolute with regard to history. History is worked over by the ruptures of history, in which a judgement is borne upon it. When man truly approaches the Other he is uprooted from history. But the “first question in the inter-human” is “the question of justice.” “The ethical order,” deriving its measure from the realm of messianic prophecy, “does not merely prepare us for the Divinity; it is the very accession to the Divinity. All the rest is dream” (Levinas 1990: 102). There is an anarchic responsibility which summons me from nowhere into a present time! And what if it is “the measure . . . of an immemorial freedom that is older than being, or decisions, or deeds?” “There is a paradox in responsibility, in that I am obliged without this obligation having begun in me, as though an order slipped into my consciousness like a thief But this is impossible in a consciousness, and clearly indicates that we are no longer in the element of consciousness” (Levinas 1981: 13).

Pope Francis is entering history not like Bernard of Clairvoix but like Francis of Assisi taking not the route of Crusade but a call to dialogue of communication in spirit and communion of human brotherhood. Bernard was the preacher of crusade while Francis was dialoguing even in the time of crusade. Extremist thinkers and terrorist activities are no more fictions they are among us. But there are also a lot of sensible men and women among us who want to live peacefully with all. Even within the Catholic Church Islamphobia is growing. Even though Catholics in Kerala had a quality of being cultured and fare minded even some laity and even clerics are coming out and start preaching hatred. The Pope’s ways are abandoned with dangerous communal hate speech. Providing insights on contemporary realities such as the COVID-19 pandemic and social media, the encyclical is still a very traditional document. Pope Francis makes reference to the Scriptures, Church Fathers, and thinkers as diverse as Aristotle, Thomas Aquinas, and Paul Ricoeur. He notes that while he writes from Christian convictions, he intends “to dialogue among all people of good will” (FT 6). In light of this, it’s not surprising that he manifests esteem for the wisdom of Rabbi Hillel (FT 59)

and Mahatma Gandhi (FT 286) and that he highlights the 2019 Document on Human Fraternity for World Peace and Living Together that he signed with the Grand Imam Ahmad Al-Tayyeb of Al-Azhar (FT 192 and 285). “History is worked over by the ruptures of history, in which a judgement is borne upon it. When man truly approaches the Other, he is uprooted from history” (Levinas 1969: 52). The perception oriented toward revelation and sacred language because God is at work in religions. The Last Judgement of God is decisive, but the judgement is of all the instants in time, when the living is judged. Whenever divine power enters into the secular world it breathes destruction, the breach of the totality. Each instant of historical time in which action commences is a birth and breaks the continuous time of history of violence and subjugation.

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